

Research Paper

Effect of coupler tip size on round window stimulation with the floating mass transducer under controlled preload

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Mechanical stimulation of the cochlear round window (RW) extends the indication of active middle-ear implants to mixed and conductive hearing loss, yet outcomes vary considerably due to transducer–RW size mismatch and uncontrolled preload. The Hannover Coupler version 2 (HC2) addresses these issues with a small tip and a force indicator. This study further evaluates the effect of HC2 tip size on RW stimulation efficiency under controlled preload force.

Methods: Stapes displacements were measured in six human temporal bones using laser Doppler vibrometry during acoustic and RW stimulation. The RW was stimulated by a floating mass transducer (FMT) with three HC2 tip diameters: small (0.5 mm), medium (0.7 mm), and large (1.0 mm). RW preload ranged from 4 to 60 mN.

Results: The large HC2 tip produced the highest transfer function magnitude and average equivalent sound pressure level across speech-relevant frequencies (0.5–4 kHz), peaking at a preload of 30 mN—approximately 11 dB higher than the small tip. Differences between large and small tips were significant at nearly all preload, whereas medium and small tips showed no significant differences. Optimal preload for FMT depended on coupler tip size: 15 mN (small), 25 mN (medium), and 30 mN (large).

Conclusion: RW stimulation efficiency increases with HC2 tip size. The large tip provides the highest output and lowest RW membrane stress, reducing penetration risk. FMT stimulation with different HC2 tip sizes has distinct optimal preload. These findings support the use of a larger HC2 tip to improve clinical outcomes in RW stimulation.

1. Introduction

Hearing loss is the third leading cause of disability worldwide, affecting more than 1.5 billion people, of whom approximately 430 million have disabling hearing loss (Haile et al., 2021). Most patients turn to hearing aids, which rehabilitate hearing by providing acoustic stimulation. However, these devices are constrained by intrinsic shortcomings, including insufficient amplification at high frequencies, occlusion effects within the external auditory canal, and signal distortions. Consequently, a substantial proportion of candidates who could benefit from hearing aids ultimately choose not to use them (Burovikhin et al., 2023). Accordingly, active middle-ear implants (AMEIs), which restore hearing through mechanical stimulation delivered by implanted

transducers, have undergone significant technological development over the past three decades (Banakis Hartl and Jenkins, 2020).

AMEIs are primarily designed to couple vibratory stimuli to the intact ossicular chain for treating sensorineural hearing loss (Ball and Rose-Eichberger, 2021; Seidman, Janz and Shohet, 2019). This form of AMEI stimulation is termed forward stimulation because its transmission path follows that of normal hearing (Stieger, Rosowski and Nakajima, 2013). In some cases, however, the intact ossicular chain is unavailable due to e.g. chronic otitis media, extensive otosclerosis, or congenital malformation. To address this, Colletti et al. clinically investigated a new approach in which they directly placed the floating mass transducer (FMT, Vibrant Soundbridge, MED-EL GmbH, Innsbruck, Austria) onto the cochlear other window—the round window (RW)

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(Colletti et al., 2006). This RW stimulation, also called reverse stimulation, bypasses damaged ossicles and extends AMEIs indications to conductive and mixed hearing loss (Jenkins, Greene and Tollin, 2021). Nevertheless, clinical outcomes show substantial variability among patients (Rahne et al., 2021; Sprinzel et al., 2011; Zahnert et al., 2016). The substantial variability in the provided output, irrespective of the degree of hearing loss, indicates an inherent variability in stimulation efficiency.

To uncover the causes of the large variations and improve the sound transfer efficiency to the cochlea, numerous studies have been conducted. Based on measuring the stapes velocities in human temporal bones, Nakajima et al. found that the geometry mismatch between the FMT diameter (1.8 mm) and the round window membrane (RWM) diameter (~1.5–1.9 mm) is one of the main reasons (Nakajima et al., 2010). Inserting a piece of soft tissue between the FMT and RW, which fills the space between them and prevents the FMT from hitting the bony structure around the RW, will facilitate their physical coupling (Arnold et al., 2010; Nakajima et al., 2010). However, compared with direct FMT-RW contact, this interposed soft tissue reduced the coupling efficiency (Liu et al., 2025; Marino et al., 2015; Rajan et al., 2011) and was degraded by the body (Marino et al., 2015; Pennings et al., 2010). These findings motivated the development of dedicated RW-specific transducers or couplers (Marino et al., 2015; Nakajima et al., 2010).

For round window stimulation, the transducer must contact the RWM to effectively transmit vibrational energy to the cochlea (Arnold et al., 2010). The static contact force exerted by the transducer on the RWM is referred to as the preload force (Salcher et al., 2014). Commonly, during surgery, cartilage or connective tissue is placed behind the FMT to ensure contact with the RWM; however, the resulting preload is generally undefined (Lenarz et al., 2018). Temporal bone experiments have shown that this undefined preload is another major contributor to the high variability in stimulation efficiency (Maier et al., 2013; Salcher et al., 2014). The transducer and cochlea together constitute a mechanical system for vibration transmission from the transducer to the cochlea. Vibration generated by the transducer, transmitted through the RWM into the cochlea evokes an output response at the oval window, which drives the stapes footplate (SFP). Although, this transfer function (TF) from vibration input to SFP

vibratory response has some limitations in reverse stimulation (Stieger, Rosowski and Nakajima, 2013), the TF reflects the RW stimulation efficiency, thereby influencing the input to the cochlea and ultimately the sound perception. In tests on ten temporal bones, Muller et al. found that the RW stimulation's transfer function of the FMT increased monotonically with increasing preload. Furthermore, increasing the FMT preload reduced the stapes response at lower frequencies while enhancing the response at higher frequencies (Muller et al., 2018).

To address geometric mismatch problem and standardize the coupling between the FMT and RW membrane, several couplers with modified tips have been developed (Frear and Nakajima, 2022; Muller et al., 2017). The RW coupler (RWC) with a spherical titanium tip (Zahnert et al., 2018) and the RW soft (RWS) coupler with a conical silicone tip (Rahne et al., 2021), introduced in 2010 and 2014, respectively, improved FMT transmission to the cochlea. However, both required cartilage stabilization (Fig. 1.a), leaving preload undefined and reducing low-frequency output due to cartilage high stiffness (Gostian et al., 2016; Maier et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2022). To overcome these drawbacks, the custom-made Hannover Coupler version 2 (HC2), featuring a small ball tip, soft rear spring, and preload indicator (Fig. 1.b), was developed (Muller et al., 2018). Clinical studies demonstrated that the HC2 provided stable speech recognition (Knolke et al., 2022) and smallest interpatient variability (Knolke et al., 2025).

Despite these advances, there is still no consensus regarding the optimal coupler tip size. Using a piezoelectric transducer from Otologics LLC (Boulder, CO, USA), Tringali et al. (Tringali et al., 2010) reported that a 0.5-mm tip provided a 6 dB advantage over a 1.0-mm tip at high frequencies. In contrast, using a piezoelectric stack, Schraven et al. found that a 1.0-mm-diameter rod with a 30° inclined tip outperformed a 0.5-mm-diameter rod with the same geometry (Schraven et al., 2012). This discrepancy may come from the uncontrolled preload on the RW membrane during experiments (Gostian et al., 2016). Notably, these studies focused on piezoelectric transducers, and it remains unclear whether their findings apply to the FMT, the only electromagnetic AMEI transducer currently available.

Accordingly, the present study aimed to investigate FMT–RW coupling with respect to coupler tip size on RW stimulation efficiency under controlled preload. Human temporal bone experiments were

Fig. 1. Round window stimulation with the active middle-ear implant Vibrant Soundbridge. (a) Floating Mass Transducer (FMT) directly placed on the round window membrane. (b) The previously reported Hannover Coupler version 2 (HC2) with a 0.5 mm diameter spherical tip. (c)–(e) The three investigated HC2 variants with different spherical cap-shaped tips: (c) large tip with a base diameter of 1.0 mm, (d) medium tip with a base diameter of 0.7 mm, and (e) small tip with a base diameter of 0.5 mm.

conducted using the Hannover Coupler version 2.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Design of the hannover coupler version 2

To optimize transducer coupling to the round window (RW) and control preload, we developed the Hannover Coupler (HC) for the floating mass transducer (FMT) (Muller et al., 2017). Temporal bone studies (Muller et al., 2017) and clinical data (Lenarz et al., 2018) showed that the HC improved coupling between the FMT and RW membrane at frequencies above 1 kHz. To further enhance low-frequency performance (≤ 1 kHz), the coupler was redesigned with an S-shaped softer spring (Muller et al., 2018). Clinical outcomes indicate that the HC2 provides stable speech recognition superior to RW coupling without a coupler or with the RW soft coupler (Knolke et al., 2022).

The detailed structure and design process of the HC2 were reported previously (Muller et al., 2018). Briefly, the HC2 is a lightweight titanium prosthesis consisting of four laser-welded parts: tip, frame, spring, and clip (Fig. 1b). The FMT body is clipped by the HC2, with axial fixation provided by the frame and radial fixation ensured by the clip. The S-shaped spring at the rear of the frame controls the preload applied to the RW membrane, which can be monitored via a preload indicator. The tip is spherical, allowing it to self-center on the RW membrane under consistent preload. The diameter of the spherical tip ($d = 0.5$ mm) is well below the typical RW diameter (mean smallest diameter 1.54 mm) (Atturo, Barbara and Rask-Andersen, 2014).

To assess the effect of coupler tip size on RW stimulation, three HC2 couplers with different 3D-printed spherical cap-shaped tips were used: HC2 with a large tip (HC2-L), medium tip (HC2-M), and small tip (HC2-S) (Fig. 1c-e). The tips differ in base diameter at the RW: HC2-L, 1.0 mm (surface area $A_{HC2-L} = 0.9$ mm²); HC2-M, 0.7 mm (surface area $A_{HC2-M} = 0.4$ mm²); and HC2-S, 0.5 mm (surface area $A_{HC2-S} = 0.2$ mm²). The front surfaces are spherical with an increased diameter of 1.5 mm, compared with the previous HC tip diameter of 0.5 mm. This design aims to increase the contact area between the tip and the RW membrane under the same preload, reducing RW membrane stress and minimizing penetration risk.

2.2. Temporal bones preparation and reference measurements

Experiments were conducted on six human temporal bones (TBs) with ethics approval by the ethics committee of the Hannover Medical School (11164_BO_K_2023). Specimens were stored at -21 °C and thawed on the day of the experiment, with periodic saline rinsing to prevent drying. A posterior tympanotomy was performed to access the middle ear and RW membrane; the facial nerve was dissected, and the RW niche overhang carefully removed. TBs were clamped on a magnetic stand located on a vibration-isolation table (LW3048B, Newport, Germany).

Acoustic stimulation of the tympanic membrane (TM) was delivered via a closed sound applicator cemented into the external ear canal and driven by a loudspeaker (DT48, Beyerdynamic, Germany) with a buffer amplifier (SA1, Tucker-Davis Technologies, USA), as shown in Fig. 2.a. Sound pressure was measured 1–2 mm from the TM using a flexible silicone tube attached to a probe microphone (ER-7C, Etymotic Research, USA). Stapes displacement was recorded with a laser-Doppler vibrometer (LDV) system (CLV700, HLV1000, Polytec, Germany) on a micromanipulator (HLV-MM30, Polytec, Germany) mounted to a surgical microscope (OPMI-1, Zeiss, Germany). A small piece of reflective tape ($<0.5 \times 0.5$ mm) was placed on the stapes crus to enhance reflected light intensity. The incidence angle between the LDV laser beam and the stapes footplate normal was estimated, and measurements were corrected using a cosine correction.

Based on the measured sound pressure at the TM and the resulting stapes displacement, the middle ear transfer function (METF) of all TBs was evaluated according to ASTM standard (ASTM-International-F2504–05, 2005) and Koch et al. (Koch et al., 2022).

2.3. Round window stimulation with the HC2/FMT

In RW stimulation experiments, three selected FMTs of the Vibrant Soundbridge were clamped on three Hannover Couplers, with three different tips. Different FMTs for the HC2-L, HC2-M, and the HC2-S with similar unloaded response characteristic were used to avoid repeated reinstallation and mechanical changes of the HC2 connection. Before and after experiments FMT/HC2 assemblies were tested without load for functionality. The rear ends of the HC springs were glued to threaded rods and sequentially fixed on a force sensor (LSB 210, Futek Advanced Sensor Technology, USA) for experiments, as shown in Fig. 2.b. The

Fig. 2. Schematic of the temporal bone measurement setup. (a) Measurement setup for acoustic stimulation via the external auditory canal. (b) Measurement setup for round window stimulation using the FMT/HC2. The FMT/HC2 is held by a rod mounted to a force sensor, which in turn is held by a micromanipulator. The micromanipulator can be adjusted relative to the round window membrane to control the position and the preload.

opposite side of the force sensor was fixed to a metal rod mounted on a three-axis micromanipulator (MM3301, WPI, Germany) on a magnetic stand. The HC/FMT assembly was oriented perpendicular to the RW membrane, with the HC2 tip approximately 100 μm from the RW membrane. This position was taken as the starting point, and the force sensor was zeroed. Visual inspection confirmed that the tip did not contact surrounding bone structures at the initial position and throughout experiments.

Following initialization, the HC2-L/FMT was advanced toward the RW membrane using the micromanipulator until the force sensor read 4 mN, establishing our initially tested preload. The FMT was then stimulated with a 100 mV_p input voltage using a buffer amplifier (SA1, Tucker-Davis Technologies, USA), and both stapes and HC2 tip vibrations were recorded with the LDV. These steps were repeated for additional preloads of 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, and 60 mN.

The measurements were repeated for the other two different assemblies, i.e., HC2-M/FMT and HC2-S/FMT. To quantify the output, the ASTM F2504–05 standard method (ASTM-International-F2504–05, 2005) was applied to determine the AMEIs' equivalent sound pressure level (eqSPL) from SFP vibration in response to sound and actuator stimulation, analogous to forward stimulation.

2.4. Data acquisition and acoustic stimulation

Stimulus generation for the loudspeaker and FMT, and data acquisition from the microphone and LDV, were performed using a USB-4431 data acquisition card (National Instruments, USA) controlled by a custom LabVIEW program (LabVIEW 2015). The stimulus was a stepped-sine sequence of 23 logarithmically spaced sine waves from 100 to 10,000 Hz. A buffer amplifier (SA1, Tucker-Davis Technologies, USA) provided the required power. Data were sampled at 25,600 Hz and averaged 50–300 times to achieve a signal-to-noise ratio SNR ≥ 12 dB.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test; however, due to the small sample size ($n = 6$), normality could not be assumed. Therefore, median values were used to represent the eqSPL of different tips. For statistical comparisons across HC2 tips, the Friedman test was applied, followed by a post-hoc Conover test with Holm correction to identify significant differences. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data analysis and visualization were performed using MATLAB R2024b (MathWorks, USA) and Python 3.11.8 (Python Software Foundation, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Stapes response to acoustic stimulation without RW loading

Fig. 3 shows the stapes displacement magnitude for all TBs ($N = 6$) relative to the sound pressure applied at the tympanic membrane, compared with the ASTM standard (ASTM-International-F2504–05, 2005) and the alternative range proposed by Koch et al. (Koch et al., 2022). Except for TB 4, the responses were generally within the ASTM acceptance range, and all six TBs were almost within the modified range.

3.2. Stapes responses to RW stimulation

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 present the median stapes displacement evoked by RW stimulation with the HC2/FMT under varying preload. Increasing preload reduced displacement at low frequencies but enhanced it at higher frequencies. The dependence of the RW-stimulated SFP displacement on the applied preload force was markedly stronger at low frequencies than at frequencies above ~ 1.5 kHz.

3.3. Transfer function between HC2 tip and stapes

Fig. 6 shows the median transfer functions (TFs) between the FMT, measured at the HC2 tip, and the stapes for different tip sizes. For all HC2 tip sizes, the TF amplitude increased with preload, most prominently at low frequencies (< 500 Hz).

To facilitate comparison of tip-size effects on the transfer function, Fig. 7 presents the TFs of different HC2 tips under identical preload. The TF magnitude of the large tip (HC2-L) exceeded that of the medium (HC2-M) and small (HC2-S) tips, particularly at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz). This advantage of the HC2-L increased with preload up to 20 mN but declined at higher preload. The TF of the medium tip (HC2-M) was slightly greater than that of the small tip (HC2-S) at frequencies below 3 kHz.

To further compare the TF between the three HC2 tips at speech relevant frequencies, we calculated the average TF of speech relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, 4 kHz) under different preloads in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT, as shown in Fig. 8. The precise p -values for Fig. 8b are listed in Table 1. The averaged transfer function magnitudes for individual temporal bones are provided in Supplementary Figures 1. The data in Fig. 8 indicate that the FMT with the large tip (HC2-L) generated the highest median TF magnitude across all preload levels. This advantage of HC2-L was statistically significant over preload ≥ 15 mN when compared to the HC2-S, with a maximum increase of 16 dB at

Fig. 3. Stapes displacement in response to sound stimulation of 94 dB SPL at the tympanic membrane with an unloaded RW in all tested temporal bones ($N = 6$), compared with reference data (ASTM-International-F2504–05, 2005; Koch et al., 2022).

Fig. 4. Median stapes displacement in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT at a nominal $1 V_p$ FMT input as a function of frequency for: (a) HC2 with small tip (HC2-S), (b) HC2 with medium tip (HC2-M), and (c) HC2 with large tip (HC2-L). HC2 indicates Hannover Coupler version 2.

Fig. 5. Median stapes displacement across nine frequencies in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT at a nominal $1 V_p$ FMT input as a function of preload force for: (a) HC2 with small tip (HC2-S), (b) HC2 with medium tip (HC2-M), and (c) HC2 with large tip (HC2-L).

Fig. 6. Median ($n = 6$) transfer function between the FMT, measured at the HC2 tip, and the stapes for tips of different sizes: (a) small tip, (b) medium tip, (c) large tip.

15 mN and more than 10 dB at other preload levels. However, compared with the HC2-M, the TF of the HC2-L did not show significant

Fig. 7. Median ($n = 6$) transfer function between the FMT, measured at the HC2 tip, and the stapes for each preload: (a) 4 mN, (b) 10 mN, (c) 15 mN, (d) 20 mN, (e) 25 mN, (f) 30 mN, (g) 40 mN, (h) 60 mN. Colored lines indicate the median across six temporal bones, and shaded areas of corresponding colors represent the interquartile range.

Fig. 8. Averaged transfer function between the HC2 tip and the stapes at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT. (a) Transfer function magnitudes for different HC2 tips. Colored lines indicate the median across six temporal bones, shaded areas of corresponding colors represent the interquartile range, and dots show individual temporal bone results. (b) Significant differences ($p < 0.05$; \times) between tip size groups, evaluated for each preload force.

differences. Similarly, no significant differences were observed between the HC2-M and HC2-S for most preload levels, except at 25 mN ($p = 0.0206$; Table 1), where the HC2-M produces a TF that was 13 dB larger than that of the HC2-S. Fig. 8 also shows that the optimal preload forces to achieve maximum TF were 15 mN for HC2-L, 25 mN for HC2-M, and

30 mN for HC2-S. Supplementary Figure 1 shows that the observed trend (i.e., the FMT with the large tip generated a higher TF than the small tip) was consistent across all specimens.

Table 1

Statistical comparison of the averaged transfer function between the HC2 tip and the stapes at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT with the small tip (HC2-S), medium tip (HC2-M) and large tip (HC2-L).

Comparison	Preload /mN							
	4	10	15	20	25	30	40	60
Friedman	0.0421	0.2231	0.0155	0.0302	0.0094	0.0111	0.0094	0.0155
Small vs Medium	0.1837	0.3730	0.1329	0.1695	0.0206	0.0519	0.1695	0.2359
Small vs Large	0.0524	0.0638	0.0058	0.0099	0.0131	0.0203	0.0099	0.0308
Medium vs Large	0.3983	0.2382	0.1329	0.1695	0.6813	0.5143	0.1695	0.2359

3.4. Equivalent sound pressure level

Fig. 9 shows the average equivalent sound pressure level at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5–4 kHz) in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT at a nominal 1 V_p input. The precise p-values for Fig. 9b are listed in Table 2. The results indicate that the FMT with the large HC2 tip (HC2-L) produces the highest eqSPL, particularly at low preload forces (< 30 mN), showing increases of 6–11 dB compared to the small HC2 tip (HC2-S). This difference was statistically significant across all preload forces except 4 mN (p = 0.4700; Table 2), 10 mN (p = 0.2525; Table 2), and 60 mN (p = 1.0000; Table 2). Significant differences were also observed between the large and medium tips at preload forces of 15 mN (p = 0.0281; Table 2), 20 mN (p = 0.0056; Table 2), and 25 mN (p = 0.0431; Table 2). The medium tip did not show significant improvement over the small tip. Unlike Fig. 8, Fig. 9 indicates that the optimal preload forces to achieve maximum eqSPL were 30 mN for HC2-L, 25 mN for HC2-M, and 15 mN for HC2-S. The averaged equivalent sound pressure levels for the individual temporal bones are provided in Supplementary Figure 2, which also shows that the FMT with the large tip generated a higher eqSPL than the small tip across all tested temporal bones.

3.5. Total harmonic distortion

Fig. 10 shows the total harmonic distortions (THDs) measured at the HC2 tips and stapes in RW stimulation for four sinusoidal FMT inputs (500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 Hz) under different RW preloads. The driving voltage of the FMT was 100 mV_p. The THD was calculated from the fundamental and up to its first five harmonics in the range < 10 kHz above noise floor. Fig. 10 demonstrates that the THDs were most pronounced at 500 Hz. At 500 Hz, the HC2-S, measured at the HC2 tip, got the smallest THD, reaching a minimum of 2 % at 4 mN. Measured at the

stapes, the HC2-L got the smallest THD under preload >= 20mN, reaching a minimum of 3.3 % at 20 mN. At 1 kHz, the THD generally increased with preload for all the three HC2 couplers, with HC2-M having the highest value of 9.5 % at the tip and 18.5 % at the stapes (both at 60 mN). Under low preload (< 15 mN for HC2 tip, < 25 mN for Stapes), HC2-L produced lower THD than HC2-S. At 2 kHz, all the THDs remained below 3 % for the three HC2 couplers, with HC2-L consistently lowest (<0.3 % under all preloads). At 4 kHz, all tips THD stayed below 2 %. Across preloads, HC2 tip THD of HC2-S was slightly higher than that of HC2-L.

To facilitate the comparison of a specific HC2 tip, we also plot the THD of different tips, as shown in Fig. 11. The results demonstrate that, for all HC2 tips, the THD exhibits a generally decreasing trend with increasing frequency. At frequencies >= 1600 Hz, the THD values of all tips remain below 2 %.

4. Discussion

RW stimulation with the FMT extends the indications of AMEIs to conductive and mixed hearing loss, but clinical outcomes show substantial variability among patients (Rahne et al., 2021; Sprinzl et al., 2011; Zahnert et al., 2016). Diameter mismatch between the FMT and RW, together with uncontrolled preload, are two primary contributing factors. To address these issues, our group developed the Hannover Coupler version 2 (Muller et al., 2018), designed to address both factors simultaneously. Clinical data demonstrated that the HC2 provided stable speech recognition (Koch et al., 2022) and smallest interpatient variability (Knolke et al., 2025).

The present study aims to further investigate the influence of coupler tip size on the RW stimulation under controlled preload. Related temporal bone studies (Schraven et al., 2012; Tringali et al., 2010) have

Fig. 9. Averaged equivalent sound pressure level (eqSPL) at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT at a nominal 1 V_p FMT input. (a) eqSPL for different HC2 tips. Colored lines indicate the median across six temporal bones, shaded areas of corresponding colors represent the interquartile range, and dots show individual temporal bone results. (b) Significant differences (p < 0.05; ×) between tip size groups, evaluated for each preload force.

Table 2

Statistical comparison of the averaged equivalent sound pressure level at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz) in response to RW stimulation by the HC2/FMT with the small tip (HC2-S), medium tip (HC2-M) and large tip (HC2-L).

Comparison	Preload /mN							
	4	10	15	20	25	30	40	60
Friedman	0.3114	0.1353	0.0094	0.0094	0.0155	0.0155	0.0302	0.6065
Small vs Medium	0.5821	0.9547	0.7394	0.5955	0.3818	0.1695	0.255	1.0000
Small vs Large	0.4700	0.2525	0.0212	0.0028	0.0104	0.0099	0.0252	1.0000
Medium vs Large	0.2761	0.2525	0.0281	0.0056	0.0431	0.1695	0.2550	1.0000

Fig. 10. Total harmonic distortion of different frequencies measured at the HC2 tips (upper row, a - d) and stapes (lower row, e - h) under FMT RW stimulation at 100 mV_p input voltage. Colored lines indicate the median across six temporal bones, and shaded areas of corresponding colors represent the interquartile range.

reported for piezoelectric transducers, but not for FMT, which is electromagnetic.

Although these mentioned earlier studies provide important insight into reverse stimulation efficiency, the present investigation aims to control and separate both factors: static preload force and tip size effects. Under controlled preload conditions, we found that the FMT with the large tip outperformed the small tip with statistical significance. In addition, different tip sizes exhibited distinct optimal preload requirements.

4.1. Tip size influence on the RW stimulation transfer function

Our results show that increasing the HC2 tip size enhanced the transfer function (TF) magnitude from the FMT to the stapes, particularly at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5–4 kHz; Fig. 7). Under optimal preloads, the large tip’s averaged TF (@15 mN) exceeded that of the small tip (@30 mN) by 12.5 dB (Fig. 8a), closely matching the ratio of their surface areas ($A_{HC2-L} / A_{HC2-S} = 13$ dB). This aligns with Schraven et al. (Schraven et al., 2012), who found a 1.0-mm tip outperformed a

0.5-mm tip, although their observed increase was only 6 dB—likely because they glued larger silicone pads (diameter=1.9 mm) to their tips, diminishing the effect of tip size. In addition, their comparison experiments were performed under an uncontrolled (unknown) preload force. Nevertheless, our results indicated that preload affected the RW stimulation TF magnitude at speech-relevant frequencies, with a difference of approximately 5 dB for the large tip and 3 dB for the small tip (Fig. 8a).

We observed that the RW stimulation TF increased with preload. Below optimal preloads (15 mN for HC2-L, 25 mN for HC2-M, and 30 mN for HC2-S), the averaged TF at speech-relevant frequencies (0.5–4 kHz) rose with increasing preload, consistent with our previous study using a 0.5-mm-diameter spherical tip (Maier et al., 2013).

4.2. Tip size influence on RW stimulation equivalent sound pressure level

We found that the FMT with the large tip (HC2-L) produced the highest average equivalent sound pressure level across speech-relevant frequencies (0.5–4 kHz) compared with HC2-M and HC2-S. Under optimal preloads, the large tip’s eqSPL (@30 mN) exceeded that of the

Fig. 11. Total harmonic distortion (median across six temporal bones) of different tips measured at the HC2 tips (upper row, a – c) and stapes (lower row, d – f) under FMT RW stimulation at 100 mV_p input voltage.

small tip (@15 mN) by 8 dB (Fig. 9). The 8 dB increase in eqSPL due to tip size was smaller than the ratio of the corresponding tip surface areas ($A_{HC2-L} / A_{HC2-S} = 13$ dB). This difference might be due to the electromagnetic FMT principle (Bornitz, Hardtke and Zahnert, 2010); increasing the tip size also raises the input impedance to the cochlea, thereby reducing the output displacement of the FMT with the large tip (HC2-L).

4.3. Tip size influence on RW stimulation optimal preload

Preload is a key determinant of RW stimulation output (Gostian et al., 2016; Maier et al., 2013). Our previous experiments showed that the Hannover Coupler version 2 with a 0.5-mm-diameter ball tip achieved its optimal performance at a preload of 15 mN (Muller et al., 2018). This study further reveals that the optimal preload depends on coupler tip size. For RW stimulation transfer function magnitude, the optimal preload decreases with increasing tip size: 15 mN for the large tip (HC2-L), 25 mN for the medium tip (HC2-M), and 30 mN for the small tip (HC2-S).

However, for equivalent sound pressure level, the optimal preloads for the medium and larger tips shifted to 25 mN (HC2-M) and 30 mN (HC2-L), respectively. This shift in optimal preload arises from changes in the FMT's output caused by variations in output impedance associated with HC2 tip size. Notably, the optimal preload for HC2-L (15 mN) is the same as that reported for a 0.5-mm-diameter spherical tip (Muller et al., 2018).

4.4. Tip size influence on RW stimulation total harmonic distortion

For all HC2 couplers, total harmonic distortion (THD) at the HC2 tips

and stapes was highest at 500 Hz but generally low at 1, 2, and 4 kHz, consistent with our previous findings (Muller et al., 2017, 2018). The elevated THD at 500 Hz likely reflects the FMT's force-dependent resonance near 1.5 kHz, producing a pronounced third-harmonic relative to the 500 Hz fundamental (Muller et al., 2017). At 2 and 4 kHz, the large tip (HC2-L) exhibited the lowest THD (<0.4 %) across all preload conditions compared with the medium and small tips, offering a notable advantage for speech intelligibility (Amlani, Punch and Ching, 2002).

4.5. Tip size influence on the RW membrane stress

Although the optimal preload for the large tip (30 mN) is higher than that for the small tip (15 mN), the stress on the RW membrane under the large tip remains lower than that of the small tip at their respective optimal preloads. Assuming full contact between the HC2 tips and the RW membrane and uniform stress distribution, the RW membrane stress for the large tip under optimal preload ($30 \text{ mN} / 0.9 \text{ mm}^2 = 33.3 \text{ kPa}$) is considerably lower than that for the medium tip ($25 \text{ mN} / 0.4 \text{ mm}^2 = 62.5 \text{ kPa}$) and small tip ($15 \text{ mN} / 0.2 \text{ mm}^2 = 75.0 \text{ kPa}$). This reduces the likelihood of RW membrane penetration with the HC2. Additionally, the higher allowable preload facilitates surgical handling and makes the deformation of the HC2's back spring more easily observable without exceeding the common anatomical constraints of the RW size (Nakajima et al., 2010).

4.6. The influence of variability in RW anatomy

The anatomy of the round window membrane directly influences the efficiency of the RW stimulation (Liang et al., 2021; Yao et al., 2018). Our comparative analysis of individual temporal bones (Supplementary

Figure 1) shows that the FMT with the large tip generated higher TF values than the small tip across all tested specimens. However, when compared to the medium tip, the large tip produced lower TF values in TB1, TB3, and TB4 under certain preload conditions. As the mechanical properties of the RWM do not differ significantly among individuals (Liang et al., 2021), we hypothesize this discrepancy is primarily due to interindividual variations in RWM area. An anatomical study using cone beam computed tomography imaging of 50 patients reported that RWM area varies by more than a factor of three, ranging from 1.30 to 4.39 mm², with a mean of 2.93 mm² (Matin et al., 2021). Notably, the lower limit of this range (1.30 mm²) is comparable to the area of our large tip (0.9 mm²). In such cases, the motion of the large tip against the RWM may be hindered by the bony structures surrounding the round window (Nakajima et al., 2010). A numerical study also demonstrated that increasing the coupler area from 50 % to 100 % of the RWM area can reduce RW stimulation efficiency (Zhao et al., 2022).

4.7. Limitations of this study

Several limitations of the present study should be considered. First, the sample size was limited, and all experiments were conducted on cadaveric temporal bones. Although this mode enables controlled mechanical measurements, it does not fully reflect in vivo conditions during clinical application, particularly with respect to tissue vitality, physiological loading, and long-term biomechanical behavior. Consequently, the absolute magnitude of the measured responses and their direct translation to clinical conditions is possible (Busch, Lenarz and Maier, 2025; Grossohmichen et al., 2017) but should be interpreted with caution. Future studies with a larger number of specimens will be conducted with similar prototypes that fulfil the legal requirements for clinical application are intended.

Second, detailed anatomical characterization of the round window membrane was not performed for all specimens. Variations in round window membrane thickness, curvature, and geometry are known to affect mechanical behavior and coupling efficiency. Although common in temporal bone experiments, the lack of specimen-specific anatomical data therefore represents an important source of uncertainty and may contribute to the observed inter-specimen variability.

5. Conclusion

Our experiments demonstrate that coupler tip size has a significant effect on the output of RW stimulation with the FMT. The FMT with the large tip outperformed the small tip with statistical significance. Under the optimal preload, Hannover Coupler version 2 with the large tip (HC2-L) produced an eqSPL 8 dB higher than that of the small tip (HC2-S). The FMT with HC2-L also has smallest stress on the RW membrane, and exhibited the lowest total harmonic distortion at 2 and 4 kHz across all preloads, which is critical for speech intelligibility. In addition, different HC2 tip sizes have distinct optimal preloads: 15 mN for the small tip, 25 mN for the medium tip, and 30 mN for the large tip.

For surgeons, our data suggest that the best audiological outcomes can be achieved by coupling the FMT with the Hannover Coupler version 2 using the large tip (HC2-L). The optimal preload force varies with tip size; for the large tip, it is 30 mN—twice that required for the small tip—and can be monitored relatively easily during surgery.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Houguang Liu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Ghoncheh:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Daniel Schurzig:** Methodology, Investigation. **Thomas Lenarz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Nils Prenzler:** Methodology, Investigation. **Hannes Maier:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

D. Schurzig is an employee of MED-EL. M. Ghoncheh, T. Lenarz and H. Maier received travel support by MED-EL to conferences. The authors disclose no other conflicts of interest.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.heares.2026.109565.

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